

The importance of Personal Branding in today's job market

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Abstract. Personal brands have become very important in today's competitive market; personal brand has become the most important factor affecting the success of a person at the professional level. In the world of digital platforms, social media is strengthening the relationship between employers and employees and therefore since job hunting is mostly on media platforms, personal branding plays an important role in one's success in finding a good job and advancing one's career. In this article, we explore the growing importance and benefits of personal branding for job seekers and industry professionals, particularly in recruiting professionals and trusted employees through personal branding. In this article, we conducted primary research and conducted a survey among 200 experts and used secondary data from available literature and reports. Through personal branding we can easily see the results of a strong personal brand leading to career mobility and the ability to advance and earn a higher income and we can see a clear correlation between the two. In this article we will discuss ways to create an effective personal brand the challenges faced by professionals starting a personal brand, and the potential benefits of a personal brand in today's market.

Abstract. Bugungi raqobatbardosh mehnat bozorida shaxsiy brendning professional muvaffaqiyatiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omil sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Raqamli platformalar va ijtimoiy media ish beruvchilar va ish izlovchilarning o'zaro munosabatlarini qayta belgilaganligi sababli, shaxsiy brendning shaxsiy martaba istiqbollari shakllantirishda muhim ro'l o'ynaydi. Ushbu tadqiqot ish izlovchilar va mutaxassislar uchun shaxsiy brendning ortib borayotgan ahamiyatini o'rganadi, xususan ishga yollash uchun onlayn platformalarga bo'lgan ishonch ortib borayotgani nuqtai nazaridan. U birlamchi tadqiqotlarni jumladan 200 nafar mutaxassis ishtirokidagi so'rovni mavjud adabiyotlar va sanoat hisobotlaridan olingan ikkilamchi ma'lumotlarni birlashtiradi. Natijalar kuchli shaxsiy brendning va yaxshi ish istiqbollari martaba harakatchanligi va yuqori daromad olish salohiyati o'rtasidagi aniq bog'liqlikni ko'rsatadi. Ushbu maqolada samarali shaxsiy brendni yaratish usullari, mutaxassislar duch keladigan qiyinchiliklar va zamonaviy mehnat bozorida shaxsiy brendning potensial uzoq muddatli foydalari muhokama qilinadi.

Абстракт. Современном конкурентном рынке труда личный брэндинг стал ключевым фактором влияющим на профессиональный успех. Поскольку цифровые платформы и социальные сети меняют представление о том как взаимодействуют работодателем и соискатели работы личный брэндинг играет решающую роль в формировании карьерных перспектив человека. В этом исследовании рассматривается растущая значимость личного бренда для соискателей и специалистов особенно в свете растущей зависимости от онлайн-платформ для набора персонала. Он сочетает в себе первичные исследования в том числе опрос 200 специалистов со вторичными данными из существующей литературы и отраслевых отчетов. Результаты демонстрируют четкую корреляцию между сильным личным брендом и лучшими перспективами трудоустройства карьерной мобильностью и более высоким потенциалом заработка. В данной статье рассматриваются методы создания эффективного личного бренда проблемы с которыми сталкиваются профессионалы а также потенциальные долгосрочные преимущества личного бренда на современном рынке труда.

Key words: Networking, branding, Business, professional, recruitment, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn.

1. Introduction

We all know that today social networking and media marketing is developing very widely because of this companies and brands need to promote their business and make it famous as well as to let their customers and other people know more about their company they want. Building relationships with potential employers and loyal customers is so important that it's best done online, and in the digital world personal branding is one of the most important aspects of life. There are a lot of vacancies in the labor market and accordingly there are a lot of candidates so in a competitive market we can no longer rely on methods such as resumes and interviews. The main differentiator of the personal brand is the quality of the support process creating a unique professionalism. With the availability of professional platforms such as social media and LinkedIn people can now prepare in advanced by shaping and controlling how they will be perceived by employers and clients. The importance of personal branding is so strong that employers are better able to communicate with candidates who have a strong and visually appealing personal brand and have higher hiring rates. Being able to perfectly demonstrate the work of instilling credibility with your customers through your personal brand, showing how you to are experienced in your field helps you to gain authority in the field and establish a strong connection with others. Through this article, we examined the role of personal branding in today's market by conducting primary and secondary research. It will influence job seekers and professionals alike and teach them how to effectively manage their personal brand and survive in a competitive market.

2. Literature Review

1) In recent years, personal branding has become the most relevant topic, that is it is gaining a lot of attention in academic and professional circles and because of this it has become the most expanding field. According to [1] (Peter Montoya, Tim Vandehey 2002), personal brand is a strategic method, with the help of this personal brand, people reveal their special and unique skills work experience and other personal characteristics and start to market. The author says that through a personal brands, specialists can show that they are the best specialists in their field, stand out from competitors and have a loyal audience.

2) Peters [2] (Peters 1997) who has done a lot of research also supports these ideas and states that a personal brand is not only about creating a brand image, but also describes the truest expression of one's professional skills and human values. Peters says that through a personal brand, one should show the true side of oneself, the true reflection and that successful personal brands can reach their audience regardless of who they are, whether it is an employer or a customer provides a deep resonance with them.

3) Research by Kaplan and Haenlein [3] (Kaplan and Haenlein 2010), highlights the impact of social media on personal branding. They are mainly online platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram that offer opportunities for people to communicate with their clients in their field, show them their work experience and participate professionally. This is very important today, and it also says that 70% of recruiters look at a candidate's social media activity and presence after meeting and talking to them before hiring, and they make decisions based on that.

4) In today's developing world, we all know the proliferation of literature, as well as digital portfolios and personal websites. Looking at research conducted by the National Association of Colleges and Recruiters [4] (NACE 2020), we can see that professionals and job seekers with an active and well-maintained online portfolio are not active online, but have a personal brand and are active online 40% are more employed and have higher employment rates.

3. Research Methodology

This article uses primary and secondary research to assess the role and importance of personal branding in today's job market.

• Primary research

We conducted a survey of 200 people from a variety of industries, including technology, healthcare, marketing and education. The main topic of the survey was personal branding and conducted to fully understand the practices of the field. Surveys were distributed online, there were mostly multiple-choice and open-ended questions. The most important objectives of the survey were the following:

1. The importance of personal branding in the life of professionals
2. Tools and platforms needed in the process of building a personal brand
3. The extent to which personal brand promotion is possible and the opportunities that personal brand opens up

Questions for survey:

- How important do you think personal branding is for career growth?
- How often do you actively work on building and maintaining your personal brand?
- Do you believe personal branding plays a significant role in acquiring job opportunities?
- How would you rate the impact of personal branding on your career advancement?
- Which platforms do you use most often for professional personal branding
- Do you regularly post or share content on your chosen platforms to build your personal brand?
- How much do you believe a strong personal brand helps you stand out in a competitive job market?
- How likely are you to recommend working on personal branding to your colleagues or peers for career growth?

Survey Results:

- **80,5% of our respondents** were positive about building their personal brand and choose to work on building and maintaining their personal brand.
- **83% of our respondents** believed that personal branding is of great importance in gaining clients and advancing their careers
- **63,5% of professionals** in their field use LinkedIn because they consider it to be a very important platform for professional branding and the remaining 24% believe that it is better to build a personal brand on Twitter and 27% for Instagram because it makes it

easier for them to communicate with colleagues in their field and useful for sharing experiences.

- **73% of respondents** have received job offers or career advancement opportunities because of their personal brand

- **71,5% of respondents** believe that in today's competitive market, despite the large number of specialists, it is possible to stand out from other competitors through a strong personal brand.

• **Secondary research**

In terms of secondary research, we reviewed existing research, industry reports and expert opinions on personal branding and selected relevant ones, which included:

- According to **LinkedIn's 2020** report, professionals with personal brands are beginning to influence hiring and decision-making. [5] (LinkedIn 2020) LinkedIn 2020, Workplace Learning Report 2020 | LinkedIn Learning, learning.linkedin.com, viewed 13 December 2024, <<https://learning.linkedin.com/resources/workplace-learning-report-2020>>.

- **A 2018 study by Career Builder** shows that 70% of hiring managers or employers look at a candidate's social media profile first, then their personal brand. [6] (Career Builder 2018) Career Builder 2018, CareerBuilder Challenge 2018 Golf Leaderboard - PGA TOUR - Highlights, Pgatour.com, viewed 13 December 2024, <<https://www.pgatour.com/tournaments/2018/careerbuilder-challenge/R2018002/highlights>>.

- Personal branding **books and academic articles** on personal branding are very common examples include [7] (Montoya and Vandehey 2002), [8] (Peters 1997a), [9] (Kaplan & Haenlein 2010) Montoya and Vandehey 2002, The Personal Branding Phenomenon, Google Books.

4. Research Findings

How important do you think personal branding is for career growth?
200 ОТВЕТОВ

(Figure 1)

Do you believe personal branding plays a significant role in acquiring job opportunities?

200 ответов

(Figure 2)

Which platforms do you use most often for professional personal branding?

200 ответов

(Figure 3)

Do you receive job offer or career advancement opportunities because of your personal brand

200 ответов

(Figure 4)

How much do you believe a strong personal brand helps you stand out in a competitive job market?
200 ОТВЕТОВ

(Figure 5)

5. Data Analysis

Through our survey, we can find out from the results of primary research how important the personal brand is in today's labor market. 80,5% of professionals actively pursuing their personal brand saw a direct correlation between their branding efforts and career advancement and success. Our survey found that professionals who have built a strong personal brand are more likely to receive job offers and are more likely to receive job offer from reputable companies and be more likely to advance their careers. We should also say that through the survey we found out that the majority of people prefer to create a personal brand on Instagram and that Instagram and LinkedIn are much more useful and effective.

73% of respondents believe that increased job offers or professional opportunities through a personal brand can only be achieved through a carefully managed online presence and that online presence can lead to career advancement. With LinkedIn recognized as the dominant platform, 63,5% of respondents use and are active on LinkedIn for social networking and branding and we can still see the results today.

Secondary research also supports this information. Research from (Career Builder 2018) and (LinkedIn 2020) highlights how important online presence and personal brand presence and reputation are. In the recruitment process, candidates with a digital portfolio are more likely to be referred to for candidate evaluation and recruitment. From a study by Career Builder we know that during the hiring process, 63,5% of hiring managers take their social media activity and posts too seriously, and many candidates are rejected because of the number of poorly managed personal brands and this increases the potential risks associated with personal branding.

6. Discussion

In this section we explore the role and importance of personal branding in today's growing job market and discuss in detail the research methodologies used. In the study, we used mixed methods combining **primary research** through surveys and **secondary research** through surveys and secondary research through literature review and industry reports. Through this combination, we will explore from all angles the role of personal branding in career and reputation development and how professionals and individuals can strategically navigate their careers.

• **Primary Research: Survey Methodology**

Through the primary research method, we conducted a survey and the number of participants was 200 professionals, the purpose and topic of the survey was how personal branding can be applied in real life and also to get direct insights. We polled experts from a variety of fields and this way the survey captures a wide range of perspectives and as a result we can cover the topic more broadly. The results of the survey show that 80,5% of the respondents have a personal brand and are actively engaged in it, and 85% of respondents agreed that personal branding plays a major role in career success and reputation. Our findings from this survey highlight how important personal branding is in today's growing world.

One of the most important and powerful aspects of the survey is that it reveals what professionals in the field are doing and the attitudes and behaviors of professionals in this field and the empirical evidence that shows and supports the importance of personal branding. Provides with not only this, but also through the survey the experts got clear information on how to create their personal brand and the methods that will benefit them in the process. **LinkedIn** is used by 63,5% of its users and has broader trends than seen in a secondary database such as the LinkedIn platform and accordingly emphasizes personal branding as a key component.

However, a limitation of primary research is its reliance on self-reporting. Based on the answers given by the respondents, it will be determined what their feelings are and the extent of their experiences but it may not always give a complete and accurate picture. How participants perceive branding efforts to be effective, or otherwise, directly related to their brand rather than through other factors can be. However, the large and high correlation between the votes cast by participants and their reported personal brand position, action and reputational success is significant in understanding how it affects real life.

In addition, although a survey of 200 participants was conducted and its results are generalizable to a wider population we need to expand our research in the future to draw more and more reliable conclusions possible. It can provide additional information that can include professionals from different geographic regions and different levels of citations.

Also we can clearly say that most of the participants chose **Instagram** and recognize that personal brand is very important, they can gain reputation behind it and also they can get a good and high position job through this personal brand, and we also found out from the results of the research. Most employers hire candidates based on their personal brand and online portfolio, no matter how well they passed the interview, so personal branding is very important. It is also very vital and important for every master or his work experts and professionals to have a personal brand and good social network profile and online portfolio.

• **Secondary Research: Literature review and industry reports**

As for secondary research, secondary research methodology is done by reviewing pre-existing literature and industry reports that have already been accessed to contextualize the primary research findings. By providing a historical and theoretical framework through this method and through the findings of this secondary study we will explore how and to what extent personal branding has evolved over time and exactly why it is so important and highly valued in today's growing job market. Made it possible to understand and explain the existence of personal branding.

The main advantage of a secondary study is that it allows the examination of the results of studies done by many others and provides more and wider information than relying on the results from a single survey. For example, the **Career Builder** [10] (Career Builder 2018) study found that 70% of employers and recruiters consider the extent to which they use social media to recruit and screen candidates, and use this as a key factor in hiring decisions. That is, they are hired through the importance of online presence and online portfolios. This secondary data survey allows us to confirm and support the results, which highlight the benefits of personal branding and its importance as a key factor in getting a job in today's world.

In the same way, studies such as [11] (**Kaplan and Haenlein 2010**) show the level of influence and level of influence and role of social media in personal branding and the results of studies show that the most used platform is LinkedIn and the most they pay attention to the same platform. Analyzing secondary research, another study by [12] (**Montoya and Vandehey 2002**) provides this theoretical framework by conceptualizing personal branding as a strategic and incremental process. One of their main tasks is to continue consistent cooperation with popular platforms and to create more meaningful and useful content and support the results by contributing to the work and efforts of professionals to build long-term personal brands.

However, secondary research cannot address the experiences of experts and professionals or contemporary issues as efficiently and easily as primary research. For example, while [13] (**NACE 2020**)'s report on the importance of online portfolios through personal branding across platforms is quite insightful, it does not say how experts are actually using these online portfolios or measuring whether they are working. Does not provide information. Therefore, secondary research can only offer the most relevant and important contexts, but active research with active participants has nothing to do with the accuracy of primary research.

• **Comparing Primary and Secondary research methodologies**

As a result of the combination of primary and secondary research methodology, it reveals the advantages and advantages of personal branding in the labor market. A secondary research framework that analyses personal branding based on the main theories and practices of well-recognized practices can provide more accurate information, giving confidence to raise the level in a wider context. Resulting in widespread and extensive reporting and research highlighting trends such as how social platforms are growing and the dominance of digital portfolios and their role.

On the other hand, primary research provides clearer and more understandable insights. Through survey data, today's experts in their field will learn how to adopt and implement their personal branding strategies in the right way. It can provide more specific information about the online platforms used by research professionals and the advantages of these platforms and how they overcome the challenges and difficulties they face and succeed in building their personal brands. Therefore, primary research can answer the questions "how" and "why" from a more practical side, while secondary research can answer the question "what" and "why" mainly from the theoretical and macro side. It is on these grounds and facts that these two studies differ from each other, but we must also say that both are very important studies

Primary and secondary research is a very important factor in understanding the importance of personal branding and its role in the modern and developing labor market. The respective strengths of both methods complement each other, providing a deeper and richer understanding

of the subject. While secondary research theory provides industry-wide perspectives, primary research provides a more accurate understanding of the real-life experiences of practitioners. And again, if both methods are combined they can provide a reliable analysis of the importance of personal brand in career advancement.

As a results, by taking date from both sources and combining them, personal branding can no longer be optional and reinforce the importance of career success and professional appearance in today's digital world.

7. Conclusion

Personal branding has emerged as the most powerful factor in today's increasingly competitive job market and a key factor in career development. Based on the results obtained through primary and secondary research we can say that this article provides that professionals who actively create and support their personal branding have a greater chance of achieving career success. The date also shows that a strong personal brand can not only attract job offers, but also increase career mobility, networking opportunities and higher earning potential for professionals.

As today's job market continues to evolve, personal branding is becoming an integral part of professional success. Job seekers and professionals can develop and use digital platforms, build online reputation and maintain strong relationships with and attract employers. Therefore, as a result, professionals are more likely to achieve much wider and long-term success in the digital world and earn more money.

In conclusion, personal branding today is not just an additional career tool – it is a very important tool that professionals must adopt and start building in order to stand out in the modern, evolving market it is important strategy.

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